

Ultraviolet Absorption Spectra of Arylmercuric Chlorides and Acetates

V. Baliah and P. Subbarayan

The ultraviolet spectra of a number of arylmercuric compounds have been recorded and analysed. The data indicate that mercury in these compounds can act either as an electron-acceptor or as an electron-donor, depending on the nature of the group present in *para* position.

The only study made till now on the ultraviolet absorption spectra of aromatic mercury compounds is that of Leandri and Tundo¹. The number of substituted phenylmercuric chlorides examined by them was, however, only five. It was considered necessary to study the spectra of more of such compounds in order to ascertain the influence of substituents in the benzene nucleus on the electronic distribution in the excited state. It was also thought of interest to compare the spectra of arylmercuric chlorides with those of the corresponding arylmercuric acetates. With these aims the ultraviolet spectra of a number of compounds have been recorded. The spectra of the arylmercuric chlorides are shown in Table I (see also Figs. 1-3).

TABLE I

Ar.	$\lambda_{\max}$	$\epsilon_{\max}$	Ar.	$\lambda_{\max}$	$\epsilon_{\max}$
Phenyl	259 $m\mu$	370	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	273	400
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	268	480		233	11,500
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	266	375	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	283 $m\mu$	3,300
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	263	250	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	273	2,000
	225	12,300		234	13,400
2,6-Dimethylphenyl	272	630	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	274	5,600
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	264	290	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	270	11,900
	226	17,700	<i>p</i> -Aminophenyl	252	12,200
<i>o</i> -Anisyl	280	2,700	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenyl	272	18,900
	227	5,400	<i>p</i> -Diethylaminophenyl	270	20,000
			2-Methyl-4-dimethylaminophenyl	280	13,900

In analysing the ultraviolet spectra of arylmercuric chlorides, it would be helpful to bear in mind the absorption characteristics of benzene and some of its derivatives. Benzene absorbs maximally near 260, 200, and 180 $m\mu$. The bands at 260 and 200 $m\mu$ are more easily accessible. These are referred to as the secondary band and primary band, respectively². The 260 $m\mu$ band is also called B-band³. For benzene the molecular extinction coefficients at 260 and 200 $m\mu$ are 230 and 8,000, respectively⁴. The transition

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3377.

2. Doub and Vandenberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2714.

3. Braude, *Ann. Rep. Progr. Chem.*, London, 1945, 42, 105.

4. Gillam and Stern, "Electronic Absorption Spectroscopy", Edward Arnold, London, 1955, p. 119.

at 260 $m\mu$ ($A_{1g} \rightarrow B_{2u}$) is forbidden and therefore weak. The resolution of the vibrational structure is another characteristic feature of the 260 $m\mu$ band. Attachment to the benzene ring of atoms containing lone pairs of electrons shifts the 260 $m\mu$ band to longer wave lengths and intensifies it⁵. The $A_{1g} \rightarrow B_{2u}$ transition is forbidden as a consequence of the hexagonal symmetry of the benzene molecule. Any substituent, which releases electrons to the benzene ring, removes some of the forbiddenness from the $A_{1g} \rightarrow B_{2u}$ transition, thereby intensifying the absorption.

Phenylmercuric chloride has a very weak band at 259 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 370). This is undoubtedly the benzenoid band though the vibrational structure is lacking (Fig. 1). The molecular extinction coefficient does not indicate the existence of any significant resonance interaction between the chloromercuric group and the benzene nucleus. This is understandable because mercury does not have non-bonded electrons in the outer shell. The spectra of

FIG. 1

1. Ph. HgCl.
2. *o*-Tol. HgCl.
3. *m*-Tol. HgCl.
4. *p*-Tol. HgCl.
5. DiMe. C₆H₃. HgCl.

that there must be some conjugative interaction of CH_3O - and $-HgCl$ groups through the benzene nucleus. The same can be said of the *p*-hydroxy and *p*-amino compounds. The spectra of *p*-dimethylamino- and *p*-diethylamino-phenylmercuric chloride reveal even a greater electronic interaction of the *para* substituents. The spectral behaviour of these compounds can be explained on the basis that the following structure makes an important contribution to the excited state. Such a structure depicts mercury in a trivalent state. This is possible because mercury has two vacant *p*-orbitals in its valence shell.

o-, *m*-, and *p*-tolylmercuric chlorides do not differ very much from the spectrum of phenylmercuric chloride. The primary band is seen only in the case of *p*-tolylmercuric chloride (λ_{max} 225 $m\mu$; ϵ , 12,300). The secondary band (B-band) has intensity in the order: *o*-tolyl > *m*-tolyl > *p*-tolyl. Compared to the B-band of phenylmercuric chloride, the B-bands of all the tolyl compounds have undergone a red shift. This is the usual effect of methyl substitution. 2,6-Dimethylphenylmercuric chloride has even a stronger B-band; the red shift is also greater (Fig. 1).

The spectral characteristics of arylmercuric chlorides having powerful electron-releasing or electron-attracting *para* substituents are more interesting (Fig. 2). In these compounds the primary band manifests itself as a strong long-wave length band. The primary band of anisole has maximum absorption at 220 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 7,300), whereas *p*-anisylmercuric chloride absorbs maximally at 233 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 11,500). Furthermore, the extinction coefficient of phenylmercuric chloride at 233 $m\mu$ is only about 1,250 (Fig. 2). The λ_{max} and ϵ_{max} of *p*-anisylmercuric chloride thus indicate

5. Duncan, "Electronic Spectra in the Visible and Ultraviolet Regions" in "Chemical Applications of Spectroscopy", Ed. W. West, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1956, p. 671.

FIG. 2

1. Ph. HgCl. 2. *p*-OMe. C₆H₄. HgCl. 3. *p*-Et₂N. C₆H₄. HgCl.
4. *p*-NO₂. C₆H₄. HgCl. 5. *p*-OH. C₆H₄. HgCl.

The spectrum of *p*-nitrophenylmercuric chloride is also of interest. The primary band of nitrobenzene has absorption maximum at 262 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 8,250), whereas *p*-nitrophenylmercuric chloride absorbs maximally at 270 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 11,900). The absorption of phenylmercuric chloride itself is negligible in this region. Therefore the spectral features of *p*-nitrophenylmercuric chloride may be regarded as indicating at least a weak interaction of the O₂N- and -HgCl groups through the benzene nucleus. Otherwise it is difficult to explain the λ_{max} and ϵ_{max} of *p*-nitrophenylmercuric chloride. The absence of non-bonded electrons in the valence shell makes this interaction particularly interesting. Mercury atom has the outer electronic configuration $5s^25p^65d^106s^2$. If the observed spectral effect of *p*-nitrophenylmercuric chloride is to be explained by postulating resonance interaction of the type:

5d electrons of the mercury atom must also take part in the bond formation. Here mercury acts as an electron-donor.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ultraviolet absorption spectra were obtained in 95% ethanol solution using a Beckman spectrophotometer, Model DU.

All the known arylmercuric chlorides were obtained by the methods described in the literature. The following are the melting points of pure samples: phenyl, 257-58°; *o*-tolyl, 142-43°; *m*-tolyl, 159-60°; *p*-tolyl, 233-34°; *p*-chlorophenyl, 239-40°; *o*-anisyl, 177-78°; *p*-anisyl, 244-45°; *o*-hydroxyphenyl, 151-52°; *p*-hydroxyphenyl, 226-27°; *o*-nitrophenyl, 184-85°; *p*-nitrophenyl, 265-66° (d); *p*-aminophenyl, 189-90° (d); *p*-dimethylaminophenyl, 224-25° (d); *p*-diethylaminophenyl, 162-63°.

2,6-Dimethylphenylmercuric Chloride.—To freshly distilled 2,6-dimethylaniline (12.1 g.) were added HCl (conc., 40 ml), water (20 ml), and crushed ice (20 g.). The amine hydrochloride was diazotised with sodium nitrite solution (7 g. in 15 ml of water) at 0-5°. Mercuric chloride (27.1 g.), dissolved in HCl (conc., 30 ml), was added to the clear diazonium salt solution with stirring. The temperature was maintained below 5° by addition of crushed ice (30 g.). Stirring was continued for another half an hour. The precipitate was filtered, washed twice with water (2 × 20 ml) and then repeatedly with ether. The addition compound, when dried, weighed 33 g. It was suspended in acetone (150 ml) and decomposed with cooling in water by adding precipitated copper (9.9 g.) slowly. The mixture was left overnight and the solvent was removed. The residue was washed with ethanol (20 ml) and extracted with acetone (200 ml) in a Soxhlet apparatus. Evaporation of the acetone provided 2,6-dimethylphenylmercuric chloride; yield 10.2 g. After recrystallising from ethanol, it melted at 156-57°. (Found: C, 28.24; H, 2.45. Calc. for $C_8H_{10}HgCl$: C, 28.16; H, 2.65%.)

2-Methyl-4-dimethylaminophenylmercuric Chloride.—Freshly distilled *NN*-dimethyl-*m*-toluidine (3.5 g.) was added to a cold solution of mercuric acetate (8 g.), dissolved in water (25 ml), and ethanol (12 ml), acidified with two drops of glacial acetic acid. On shaking the solution and keeping it aside, the acetate readily separated; yield 9.1 g., m.p. 131-32° (ethanol).

The above acetate (4 g.) was dissolved in hot ethanol (70 ml) and treated with a solution of sodium chloride (2 g. in 10 ml of water). The precipitate was filtered and washed with water; yield 3 g. After recrystallising from dioxane-water, it melted at 176-77°. The melting point was not depressed on admixture with a sample obtained unequivocally from 2-methyl-4-dimethylaminoaniline. (Found: C, 29.44; H, 3.32. Calc. for $C_9H_{11}NHgCl$: C, 29.19; H, 3.27%.)